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Restructuring Tertiary Education in Nigeria for Global Best Practices and Poverty Alleviation

Dr. F.O. Afolabi

Department of Educational Administration and Planning
Adeyemi College of Education, Ondo.

And

Mr. O. A. Afolabi

Department of Sociology,
University of Ibadan, Ibadan.

Abstract

The need to restructure tertiary education in Nigeria for global best practices and poverty alleviation becomes highly imperative particularly in this period of socio-economic and political vicissitudes in the country. The problem of poverty in Nigeria is an onerous, herculean and very challenging and it has been widely attributed to high rate of unemployment in Nigeria. As no nation can achieve its employment goals, and wipe out completely poverty, without emphasis on entrepreneurship education, this paper takes a cursory look at the rationale for restructuring tertiary education in Nigeria for global best practices and poverty alleviation. It identifies the various challenges and shortcomings in tertiary education, as well as causes of poverty in Nigeria. It offers measures for effective restructuring tertiary education in Nigeria for global best practices and poverty alleviation. It recommends among others that the curricula of tertiary education in Nigeria should be more pragmatic and have built-in-job training programmes, which will enable the products to acquire relevant entrepreneurial skills required for self employment and wealth creation.

Keywords: Tertiary education; Restructuring; Global best practices; poverty alleviation.

Introduction

The Nigerian government and many enlightened Nigerians perceive education as an investment in human capital, with the sole aim of wiping out various social vices and ruinous ills such as poverty, corruption, bribery, political instability, tribalism, unemployment, ignorance, malnutrition, disease, superstitious beliefs, nepotism, insecurity and economic stagnation that usually plague an illiterate society. It is re-echoed in the revised edition of the National Policy on Education (2004) that "education is an instrument that fosters the worth and development of the individual for each individual's sake and for the general development of the society". Also, Adesina (2005) succinctly remarks that, "Education should be appropriately conceived as a most powerful instrument which would not only meet the nation's social and economic aspirations, but would also develop in the individual knowledge, skills and character through a continued process". The concern and interest of Nigerian government and the entire citizenry in education is being demonstrated through huge investment in education at all levels by their various stakeholders.

Of all the levels of education in Nigeria today, tertiary education is accorded high premium by Nigerian people and Government. Tertiary education is largely conceived as a form of investment in human capital development which brings economic benefits and contributes significantly to the nation's future wealth. According to Ajayi and Afolabi (2009), tertiary education is perceived as an indispensable tool which would not only assist in meeting the nation's social, political, moral, cultural and economic aspirations, but would also inculcate in the individual knowledge, skills, dexterity, character and desirable values that would foster national development and self actualization. Also, Afolabi and Loto (2012) succinctly remarked that tertiary education is a formidable tool for scientific emancipation and technological advancement, political stability, social reconstruction, economic buoyancy and cultural integration of the nation.

In spite of the significant role of tertiary education in the development of the nation, it is, however, very disheartening that this level of education is being permeated by various shortcomings and

incertainties. If Nigeria is to forge ahead, scientifically, technologically, economically, politically and socially, tertiary education must be taken out of its present state of uncertainty, and it must be properly restructured for global best practices and poverty alleviation.

It is no superfluous that of all the critical problems facing Nigeria today, none is as devastating, persistent and agonizing as the problem of poverty among the teeming citizens. The problem has been so virulent, onerous and challenging that it has become a prominent feature of many national newspapers and magazines and Broadcasting Corporations in Nigeria.

If the teeming population of Nigeria, continues to wallow in abject poverty, the economic growth of Nigeria will be grossly retarded and the prevalent problems of insecurity of lives and property being witnessed in various parts of Nigeria such as Boko Haram Insurgencies in the North-East, Niger Delta Militia in the South-South and incessant cases of kidnapping of people for ransom or ritual in the East and West which have their genesis in joblessness and unemployment will remain unabated. As no nation can achieve its employment goals without emphasis on entrepreneurship development. Thus, effort is made in this to ascertain the efficacy of entrepreneurship education in alleviating poverty in Nigeria. As succinctly remarked by Osunji (2004), the Nigerian government strongly believes that the objectives of job creation and poverty reduction can only be realized through appropriate education which empowers the products of the education system with skills and competencies to become self-reliant". Also, Toyebi and Afolabi (2014) affirmed that "a proper integration of a able, functional and relevant entrepreneurship education into the curricula of educational institutions in Nigeria, will undoubtedly make the products acquire meaningful entrepreneurial skills and orientations that would make them self-employed and generators of employment for others". In their contribution to the importance of entrepreneurship education in alleviating poverty in Nigeria, Olojuolowe, Bello and Suntuyi (2014) declared that: "the key to poverty alleviation is economic growth and the creation of employment for all. However, for people without employable skills cannot benefit from the growth

process". The challenging task then is to raise the productive capacity of the poor and the vulnerable in various communities in Nigeria by the acquisition of job-specific competencies through entrepreneurship education.

Objectives of the Paper

The thought-provoking issues addressed in this paper are:

- (a) Why is it essential to restructure tertiary education in Nigeria for global best practices and poverty alleviation?
- (b) What are the shortcomings and uncertainties permeating tertiary education in Nigeria in recent times?
- (c) What measures are to be adopted towards proper restructuring tertiary education in Nigeria for global best practices and poverty alleviation?
- (d) What model can be set up in restructuring tertiary education in Nigeria for global best practices and poverty alleviation?
- (e) What are the causes of poverty in Nigeria?
- (f) How can the efficacy of entrepreneurship education be determined in alleviating poverty in Nigeria?

All these crucial issues are critically discussed in this paper.

Conceptualisation of Terms

Before critically examining all these thought-provoking issues, it is deemed pertinent to have a cursory look at the inherent concepts in the title of the paper. These are tertiary education; global best practices, and poverty.

(a) The Concept of Tertiary Education

According to the Fourth Edition of the National Policy on Education (2004), tertiary education is the education given after secondary education in Universities, Colleges of Education, Polytechnics, Monotechnics including institutions offering correspondence courses

(b) Global Best Practices

The concept of global best practices connotes the extent to which tertiary education in Nigeria is efficient, effective, valid, reliable, suitable and comparable to other tertiary institutions in developed

nations that accord high premium to tertiary education. Thus, tertiary education is said to be re-structured for global best practices when it possesses the inherent attributes of fitness, usefulness and appropriateness to the needs of daily life, the hopes and expectations for tomorrow and preparation for uncertainties and challenges of the unknown future. It also connotes that it adequately and effectively meets the desires and aspirations of the people yearning for tertiary education, as it focuses on the issues of relevance, effectiveness, efficiency, validity, functionalism and excellence.

(c) **The Concept of Poverty**

According to the World Bank (2006), poverty is described as:

A pronounced deprivation in well-being and comprises many dimensions. These include low income and the inability to acquire the basic goods and services necessary for survival with dignity. Poverty also encompasses low levels of health and education, poor access to clean water and sanitation, inadequate physical security, lack of voice and insufficient capacity and opportunity to better one's life.

Ekundayo (2012) also remarked that, "poverty whether absolute or relative permeates every aspect of an individual's life, including their access to education and their experience of the education processes itself. This is a disturbing fact, when education is regarded by many as the best route of escaping poverty; to help individuals improve themselves and their lot in life and as an ultimate to provide a better future for their own children".

Based on these definitions, poverty in this report is defined simply as a condition in which the income of an individual is grossly insufficient to meet such individual's subsistence needs such as nutritious food, portable water, comfortable shelter, high quality health service and basic education. Poverty also entails lack of basic capacity to participate effectively in society, due to not having enough money to feed, clothe and shelter a family and not having a job to earn one's living and lack of equilateral security to obtain credit facilities from individuals or financial institutions.

The Rationale for restructuring tertiary education in Nigeria for Global Best Practices and Poverty Alleviation

The question that imbues the mind at this juncture is, why is essential to re-structure tertiary education in Nigeria for global best practices and poverty alleviation. The answer to this question is not far fetched as the people and Government of Nigeria are now clamouring for high quality education at all levels. It is becoming glaring daily that tertiary education in Nigeria must be re-structured for global best practices and poverty alleviation because of the following reasons:

- (1) To ensure that the tertiary institutions adhere strictly to the minimum standard of operation prescribed by the educational supervisory and regulatory agencies such as National Universities Commission (NUC), National Business for Technical Education Board (NABTEB), National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE), and Quality Assurance Units or Departments of Federal and State Ministries of Education.
- (2) To break the vicious circle of poverty among Nigerian graduates through entrepreneurship education entrenched into the curricula of the tertiary institutions.
- (3) To ensure adequate production of well committed professionals with high personal and professional discipline, commendable deamemour, integrity and competence for all sectors of Nigerian economy.
- (4) To maintain and sustain good standards set for various processes and activities that lead to the production of high quality manpower for all sectors of Nigerian economy.
- (5) To produce self-reliant, well-motivated, nationally and internationally acceptable graduates with appreciable expertise in economic planning and competence in research and dissemination of knowledge.
- (6) To ensure and sustain autonomy and academic freedom in Nigerian tertiary institutions.
- (7) To continuously upgrade the lecturers through well organized regular staff development programmes so as to make them more professionally competent, zealous for social responsibility and commitment to teaching profession.

- 8) To ensure the availability and adequacy of the facilities earmarked for tertiary education programmes in Nigeria.
- 9) To ensure that the financial resources meant for the effective implementation of tertiary education in Nigeria are prudently and judiciously utilized.

The Shortcomings and Uncertainties Permeating Tertiary education in Nigeria

It is a truism that effective restructuring of tertiary education in Nigeria for global best practices and poverty alleviation, entails a critical look at the following shortcomings and uncertainties permeating tertiary education in Nigeria in recent times.

- 1) Inadequate funding of tertiary education in Nigeria. The funds allocated to the tertiary institutions by the Government or the founders in case of private tertiary institutions have been falling far short of requirement by the institutions.
- 2) Poor and obsolete infrastructural facilities in some of the tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The essential teaching and research facilities in most of the institutions are either inadequate or non-existent. While the staff welfare services are only receiving lip service in some institutions, which pave way to brain-drain syndrome.
- 3) Erosion of well orchestrated autonomy and academic freedom in some Nigerian tertiary institutions. Such institutions no longer have the freedom to internally plan, organize and administer their programmes. Ironically, teaching, research and dissemination of knowledge functions of the institutions have been subjected to government control and regulation.
- 4) It is an onerous and Herculean task to separate politics from tertiary education. For instance, the appointment of Vice-Chancellors, Rectors and Provoosts, has been greatly susceptible to political maneuvering. While staff personnel matters such as promotion, confirmation, interdiction and termination of staff appointment, discipline and staff development are being politically determined in some tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

- (5) The involvement of most undergraduates in various nefarious activities in the institutions. Such students' disruptive activities include examination malpractice, cultism, plagiarism, violent protest over welfare issues, and drug offences such as the use of cocaine, heroine and other ruinous drugs and cigarette and Indian hemp smoking.
- (6) The unethical means of balancing the education hiatus between the North and South, which has compelled the Joint Admissions and Matriculation Board to introduce quota based admission criteria into Nigerian tertiary institutions. Such criteria include merit list, catchment area, educationally disadvantaged area; and discretion list. The quota based admission system has deprived many promising Nigerian youths of higher education.
- (7) Non-involvement of many lecturers in decision-making process on vital educational matters relating to their jobs such as policy formulation, staff recruitment into Academic Departments, students placement exercise, procurement and selection of instructional resources, supervision of certain capital projects on the campuses and so on.
- (8) In some tertiary institutions that run off maincampus Sandwich, Part-Time or Preliminary Programmes, as a way of improving their internally generated revenue, there is poor administration and organization of such programmes in terms of students' admission, course duration, teaching, modes of evaluation of students' progress, certification and so on.

Measures for Restructuring Tertiary Education in Nigeria for Global Best Practices and Poverty Alleviation

- (1) **Adequate funding of Tertiary Educational Institutions:** High premium should be placed on effective funding of the institutions by all their stakeholders. These include the households, firms and other industrial establishments, philanthropists, religious organizations, and all the tiers of Government, that is, Federal, State and Local.
- (2) **Adequate Provision of Infrastructural Facilities and Modern**

Instructional Materials: Effective teaching, learning and research in the tertiary institutions in Nigeria depends greatly on availability and adequacy of physical facilities and modern instructional resources. These institutions must be provided with modern lecture rooms, lecture theatres, spacious and well conducive staff offices, well equipped automated e-libraries, well equipped laboratories and technical workshops, recreational centres and modern instructional resources. The use of Information, Communication Technologies should be integrated into all the programmes in the institutions.

3) **Integration of Entrepreneurship Education into the Curricula of Tertiary Education:** The problem of unemployment of graduates in Nigeria will be drastically reduced if entrepreneurship education is effectively entrenched into the tertiary education programmes in Nigeria. Entrepreneurship education according to Atoyebi and Afolabi (2014) is the inculcation in the individuals entrepreneurial skills, knowledge, attitudes and competences that would make such individuals live happily and successfully in the society and contribute meaningfully to its development. Entrepreneurship education according to Akanbi (2010) entails the acquisition of skills, knowledge, values and competences that make the recipient well grounded in the area of business. Thus, entrepreneurship education in tertiary education curriculum must specifically focus on how to increasingly make the products of the institutions self-employed and generators of employment for others.

The need to disentangle politics from administration of the Tertiary Institutions: To properly restructure tertiary education in Nigeria for global best practices and poverty alleviation, it is highly imperative to disentangle politics completely from the administration of the institutions, for instance, the appointment of Heads of Institutions, staff personnel administration, allocation of resources and so on must not be tainted with politics.

Proliferation of Tertiary Educational Institutions in Nigeria

should be done with caution: With the advent of the present democracy in Nigeria, in May 1999, the Federal Government, some State Governors, Religious Organizations and private individuals have made bold attempt to establish more tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The paucity of fund has compelled some of these institutions to run satellite campuses and Part-Time programmes, which put tertiary education in Nigeria into academic periphery and deteriorating standard. As a way of restructuring tertiary education in Nigeria for global best practices, attention should be focused on how to effectively fund the existing tertiary institutions, ensure that they are well staffed with highly motivated teaching and non-teaching staff and are provided with adequate modern teaching and learning resources.

(6) **The need for full professionalization of teaching in Nigeria:** Full professionalisation of teaching in Nigeria will undoubtedly make tertiary education more relevant, functional and sustainable. The Government should empower the Teachers' Registration Council of Nigeria for effective functioning. The minimum teaching qualification of NCE in Nigeria should be enforced by the Government. While lecturers in Nigerian Universities, Polytechnic, Schools of Nursing and Midwifery and Schools of Health Technology should have a teaching qualification before they are adjudged qualified to teach.

(7) **Strict adherence of the Tertiary institutions to the quality assurance strategies of the Supervisory and Regulatory bodies:** In restructuring tertiary education in Nigeria, for global best practices and poverty alleviation, all the tertiary institutions must strictly adhere to quality assurance strategies of the supervisory and regulatory bodies, that is, NUC, NABTEB and NCCCE. Such quality assurance strategies include periodic accreditation of academic programmes; laying down and reviewing minimum standards for all the institutions; laying down guidelines for establishing new institutions and mounting new programmes; external moderation system; mounting periodic staff development; streamline students' admission into

various courses, and monitoring of academic programmes and infrastructural facilities in the institutions.

A Model of Re-structuring Tertiary Education in Nigeria for Global Best Practices and Poverty Alleviation: As clearly indicated in the model depicted in figures 1, the procedural steps for re-structuring tertiary education in Nigeria for global best practices and poverty alleviation are aptly discussed as follows:

Figure 1: A model of Restructuring Tertiary Education in Nigeria for Global Best Practices and Poverty Alleviation. (Designed by the authors of the paper)

- (1) There is need for a clear identification of the government approved tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Such tertiary institutions highlighted in the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2004) include: Universities, College of Education, Polytechnics, Monotechnics and Institutions offering correspondence courses.
- (2) The objectives of tertiary education must be clearly identified and specified. The objectives of tertiary education as explicitly stated in the fourth edition of National Policy on Education are to:
 - (a) contribute to national development through high level relevant manpower training;
 - (b) develop and inculcate proper values for the survival of the individual and society;
 - (c) develop the intellectual capability of individuals to understand and appreciate their local and external environments;
 - (d) acquire both physical and intellectual skills which will enable individuals to be self-reliant and useful members of the society;
 - (e) promote and encourage scholarship and community service;
 - (f) forge and cement national unity; and
 - (g) promote national and international understanding and interaction. (FRN, 2004).
- (3) Concerted efforts must be made towards the procurement and prudent utilization of physical, material, human and fiscal resources required for effective implementation of tertiary education policies in Nigeria.
- (4) The tertiary education curricula must be highly diversified and enriched with viable entrepreneurship education.
- (5) The external supervisory and regulatory bodies such as NUC, NABTEB, NCCE, TRCN and other Teachers' Professional Organisations, as well as internal supervisors such as Institutional Heads, Deans, Directors and Heads of Departments must effectively monitor the tertiary education programmes for quality assurance and effective implementation of tertiary education policies.

-) High quality and well motivated manpower, will be produced for all sectors of Nigerian economy.
-) The high quality professionals produced in the tertiary institutions will be released into the labour market for gainful employment and economic development.

uses of Poverty in Nigeria

Lackadaisical attitude towards traditional education in Nigeria.

The Nigeria traditional education which places high priority job orientation, social responsibility, political participation, spiritual and moral values, functionalism and relevance is being looked upon being barbaric and conservative in content and nature. Consequently, many Nigerians who have received Western education, various levels are being alienated from functional existence in their communities. When the products of the Western education could not secure white-collar jobs, they become frustrated and wallow in poverty. Traditional education is employment oriented and it is directed towards meeting the basic needs of the individuals within the community. It makes the individuals self-reliant as the entrepreneurial skills acquired under traditional education can be utilized for some worthwhile commercial ventures.

Improper Integration of Entrepreneurship Education into Curricula of Nigerian Tertiary Educational Institutions

One of the aims of education in Nigeria is the acquisition of appropriate skills, abilities and competencies both mental and physical equipment for individual to live and contribute to the development of the society (FRN, 2004); This aim is in conformity with the basic aim of entrepreneurship education, that is, to give appropriate training to impact entrepreneurial skills leading to the production of utilities to ensure self-reliance. Ironically, entrepreneurship education is not properly integrated into the curricula of most tertiary educational institutions in Nigeria. The emphasis is passing specific examinations to acquire appropriate certificates. According to Adepoju (2012), "the problem is, which many job seekers possess do not match the need and

demand of employers in Nigeria. It is apparent in recent times that most educational institutions in the country have not tailored their programmes to meet the demand of work force. This makes their products ill-prepared for the labour market". Most companies have to train fresh university and polytechnic graduates in order to acquire the skills necessary to perform their role (Aregbesola, 2008). Thus, the problem of poverty would continue to be astronomical as many products of educational institutions could not secure gainful jobs, due to their lack of entrepreneurial skills.

(3) Defective Infrastructural Facilities

In Nigeria, there are various infrastructural facilities that are required for all kinds of economic activities. These include electricity, good road-network, and water supply. Information and Communication Technology facilities (ICT) and so on. If these facilities are not fully functional, defective or non-existent, then the citizenry will not be able to fully carry out their economic activities and eventually become victims of deprivation and poverty. The malfunctioning of the Electric Distribution Companies in Nigeria for not supplying regular electricity has compelled many industrial establishments in Nigeria to re-locate to neighbouring West African Countries. This situation has further aggregated the problem of unemployment and poverty in Nigeria.

(4) Poor management of resources

In recent times Nigeria has been witnessing mismanagement of resources by the people to which they are entrusted. Ironically, once these resources are being squandered or mismanaged by these custodians, the Nigerian people who are supposed to be beneficiaries are subjected to deprivation and poverty.

(5) Defective Economic Policies

It is no gainsaying that government economic policies which may prove defective in their course of implementation can bring hardship, deprivation and poverty on the citizens. In the last three decades, some economic measures introduced by the Federal Government to revamp the ailing economy have brought hardship and poverty on the citizens. Such measures include Second-tier Foreign

ge Market System (SFEM), Structural Adjustment Programme Value Added Tax (VAT), Naira Devaluation, withdrawal of es from oil and other economic policies.

High Propensity to Consume

igerians show high propensity for consumption of highly ve foreign materials. This paves way to low saving. When the s low, there will be low investible fund and consequently low ent. Low investment will pave way to low productivity, which acquiring low inputs and consequently low output and low .Thus vicious circle of poverty and economic stagnation is apparent as depicted in figure 2.

2: Vicious circle of Poverty and Economic Stagnation. (Designed by the authors of the paper)

Family Background

Extended family is quite apparent in various communities in where many children, grandchildren and other family members end on the head of the family for their livelihood. The meager es of the head of the family are being shared among the rs of such extended family, which further aggravate the problem

of poverty of the family, as the income of the head of the family is insufficient to meet subsistence needs such as food, portable water, health and basic education of the family members. Poverty in such an extended family can manifest in poor health, food insecurity, social exclusion, high crime rate, increased child labour and low illiteracy.

Ascertaining the Effectiveness of Entrepreneurship Education in Alleviating Poverty in Nigeria

(1) Wealth Creation and Income Generation

Wealth according to Aliyu (2012) "is a given quantity and quality of resource under the ownership of individuals or nations, while an income is a given amount or money earned by an individual or a nation due to an engagement in any form of legitimate economic activity". The provision of entrepreneurship education is a means for wealth creation and paves way for the alleviation of poverty in Nigeria. As depicted in figure 3, a model of functional entrepreneurship education for poverty alleviation in Nigeria. The educational inputs for entrepreneurship education include human resources such as the teaching and non-teaching staff; experienced artisans and other resource persons in the community.

The material resources include the books and periodicals and audio-visual materials; while the physical resources include the institutional buildings such as entrepreneurship centres in the institutions, classrooms, laboratories, technical workshops, libraries, administrative blocks and other physical facilities in the institutions. The financial resources refer to the available fund in the institutions.

The acquisition of entrepreneurial skills, cognitive development and development of desirable habits and attitudes through entrepreneurship education helps the recipients to become an effective entrepreneur who can hire other factors of production such as capital, land and labour for creation of utilities, wealth and income, which pave way to self reliance and employment generation.

(2) Employment Generation

Through entrepreneurship education, the entrepreneurial skills acquired will spur the entrepreneurs to set up various types of business

prises. Such businesses according to Adeyanju (2014) include dry cleaning or laundering services; manufacturing of soap and cream; interior and exterior decorations; catering and restaurant business; hair business and nourishing drinks; tie and dye or batik; bread making; soft furnishing such as headrest, arm rest, throw pillows; beads, necklaces, flowers vase, necklace and earring bead curtains; tailoring and fashion designs so on. These business enterprises will in turn employ many unemployed and other unproductive resources like idle land and abandoned land.

Improved Economic Growth

A nation that witnesses a steady improved economic growth will have a drastic reduction in the problem of poverty. According to Oluwalana (2012) "economic growth" is an increase or an expansion of the national income and the volume of goods and services in the economy. Entrepreneurship education can bring about economic growth through the establishment of various types of business enterprises and enhance the provision of Information and Communication Technologies, Information, as well as employment generation.

Effective Utilisation of Domestic or Locally Produced Cash and Resources

Poverty in Nigeria can be drastically reduced if locally produced crops and other resources are well utilized by the various large and small scale industries set up by renowned entrepreneurs in Nigeria. The effective utilization of local resources in the production of goods and services in Nigeria, will go a long way in reducing the nation's dependence on imported goods and enhance the nation's balance of payments.

Increase in Productivity

Productivity entails the desire to produce more goods and services using minimum labour, money and time. Poverty is alleviated when the attention is now focused on high productivity which is achieved through management expertise of entrepreneurs that are the products of entrepreneurship education. High productivity requires more input, which will pave way to high output and more income will be realized. This will compel the entrepreneurs to invest more and

produce more by acquiring more input. This consequently results to high output and a circle of prosperity becomes apparent.

(6) Crime reduction in Nigeria

The various nefarious activities and social vices being perpetrated particularly by many unemployed youths have their roots in poverty. Employment generation through functional entrepreneurship education will go a long way in curbing social ills such as insecurity, drug addiction, idleness, prostitution, bunkering, kidnapping for ransoms or money making rituals and so on.

Conclusion

The task of poverty alleviation is a challenging one and the approach to it differs from one nation to another. In Nigeria, poverty can be effectively eradicated through a viable and functional entrepreneurship education which must be made available to all citizens. Capital should be provided for the trained entrepreneurs to enable them establish their business enterprises that will make them to live above the poverty line. Also, concerted efforts must be made by the Government for the provision of infrastructural facilities such as good road networks, regular electricity supply, water, hospitals and Information and Communication Technology facilities. Proper restructuring of tertiary education in Nigeria entails that all stakeholders of tertiary education must provide all the necessary infrastructural support and adequate funding in support of teaching and research at the tertiary level, for the citizens to reap maximum benefit from the tertiary institutions.

Recommendations

Towards effective restructuring tertiary education in Nigeria for global best practices and poverty alleviation the following recommendations and submission are made:

The supervisory and regulatory bodies namely National Universities Commission, National Business and Technical Education Board and National Commission for Colleges of Education must be properly funded and more empowered by the Federal Government for effective service delivery.

At all phases of policy formulation and implementation on poverty alleviation, all categories of stakeholders should be full involved and meticulously carried along. Such policies must be based on relevant formation and realities on ground. Also, there is need to properly harmonise and coordinate the roles and activities of the Federal, State and Governments in the formulation and implementation of poverty alleviation policies to avoid duplication of efforts and waste of sources. Moreover, there is need to properly consider desires, needs, aspirations, priorities and peculiarities of various communities, while formulating and implementing poverty alleviation policies in Nigeria. This entails regular consultation with prominent politicians, opinion leaders and influential members of local communities.

It is highly imperative to make the curricula of tertiary institutions in Nigeria more pragmatic and have built-in-job training programmes which will enable all students to acquire relevant entrepreneurial skills required for self-employment and wealth creation. Also, every tertiary institutions in Nigeria must have spacious, aesthetically pleasing and well equipped Entrepreneurship Centre.

It is mandatory for the three tiers of government in Nigeria to encourage the Directorate of Employment, Establishment, Divisions, Micro-Finance banks and other Non-Government Organisations to provide the capital base needed for the take-off of small scale businesses and the products of entrepreneurship education for poverty alleviation and self reliance.

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